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Ecopusher: A Versatile Towboat Design Platform

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Summary

This paper discusses technical and operational challenges of inland navigation using barges + pusher convoys from the ship designer's point of view. After years of addressing the challenging requirements of this critical marine transportation mode the authors have reached an innovative towboat design approach able to combine solutions to overcome multiple operational challenges. The combination of these solutions represents a "design platform" named Ecopusher and conceived to improve competitiveness in the inland waterways transportation systems. Drastic performance improvements can be achieved by incorporating the proven alternative solutions provided by the Ecopusher platform. Authors share a few of these concept solutions inducing improved maneuvering, reduced draft and ease maintenance. They also explain the difficulties and benefits of using hybrid propulsion and green fuels. Marine lab test results are presented to back some projected improvement impacts and some ideal platform solution combinations will be mentioned for some operational cases. Finally, they address the Eureka crew training service and the operational monitoring system using a simplified digital twins' technological solution (Digitwins®) that permits handling (on line, 24/7) the performance information of the critical parameters on the operation.

1. Introduction

Each inland waterway shipping operator has a set of technical and operational requirements to be met for its future ideal fleet of towboats. Most of these requirements are related to different aspects of power, steering, fuel type and consumption, propulsion system, range, general dimensions, crew habitability and minimum draft, among others.

But in many cases, there are other non-technical client requirements as the following: preferred OEM (Official Equipment Manufacturers), shipbuilding yard, minimum local content, higher energy efficiency and reduced emissions. Minimum CAPEX, OPEX, delivery time and ease of maintenance are also at the top of the list of "musts".

Operators love to have the cheapest, cost-efficient, proven, modern solutions to be included, but without taking unexpected risks.

It all boils down to obtaining the lowest total unit cost in terms of usd/ton-km in order to get the most competitive service.

Ordering a new pusher is a very important investment decision and operators expect the most out of its design. They typically expect a "tailor made" pusher at the cost of a generic one. This is the demand side of the coin.

But the fact is that most of the towboats' designs in the market are far from innovative and have almost no room to important changes, therefore no major performance improvements have been obtained in the operation of pushers for decades. The concept design of a conventional new building pusher of today does not differ too much from one of 60 years ago. As it is very costly to develop new much better designs, most of the towboats are build based on "off the shelf" ship designs, with some cosmetic to make it "look modern".

2. Ecopusher® Design Platform

After many years of dealing with operators, shipyards and marine vendors to provide the best solution in terms of pusher design, the authors have realized that more than “a design” it was necessary to have a design “platform” versatile enough to adapt to the many different requirements in the market. This is the genesis of the Ecopusher® (protected under Intellectual Property Rights with patent pending).

Figure 1 – Ecopusher® Design Platform & its ToolKit

The design platform is a common base that combines alternative solutions for the main design factors: propulsion train (power generation and delivery system), fuel type, steering, minimum draft and range.

A careful but swift combination of the solutions takes into account the operational requirements and operator preferences, providing a really “tailor-made” design that integrates proven technologies providing a competitive solution in terms of CAPEX, OPEX, and environment impact.

Before the adoption of each solution, it has to be proved that operational performance is improved at a cost that pays back in the short term. In order to attain this, the Ecopusher® design platform works in tandem with its economic counterpart, the

MCM@Towboat (Marine Competitivity Model applied to Towboats).

The solutions to be combined have already been successfully proven and tested before being part of the Eureka Tool Kit. In the next sections eight critical aspects of a pusher design will be addressed:

- Energy Saving
- Maneuverability
- Minimum Draft
- Green Fuel
- Propulsion System
- General Arrangement
- Construction Modularity
- Performance Follow Up

3. Energy Savings

A very large amount of energy is required in the operation of a river towboat pushing loaded barges’ convoys with cargoes over 40,000dwt, in some cases navigating against strong currents of up to 6 km/h.

Therefore, it is very important to save as much energy as possible for the following three reasons:

- Cost Reduction
- Range Extension
- Harmful Emissions Reductions

This energy saving aspect can be critical for the business economics, especially when using fuels with high price volatility that can be so costly as to make the operation economically marginal.

After intensive testing and studies, Consulmar SRL, Ecopusher® designer, has identified six factors of energy savings that, when combined, can offer a reduction of over 37% of the total energy required in comparison with almost all the conventional pusher designs operating today.

Three of these items apply only to electric/gas/ batteries hybrid propulsion solutions and the rest are independent of the propulsion system.

Figure 2 – Energy Saving factors in the Ecopusher®

The six different factors summarized in Figure 2 that can provide a combined benefit in terms of energy are the following:

- 8% saving is obtained due to less fuel consumption when using a highly efficient full gas engine (SFOC: 7420 KJ/KWh) in comparison to other engines (SFOC: 8750 KJ/KWh = 190 g/WKh)
- 7,5% saving is obtained due to a better water flow to the propellers obtained from advanced water lines' design after intensive CFD modelling, combined with high performance propellers designed specifically for this use.

Figure 3 – Advanced hydrostat. and prop design

- 4,7% saving is obtained by taking out the flanking rudders that in addition to their own drag, they permanently interfere with the water flow to the propellers.

Figure 4 – Flanking rudder arrangement

- 10,4% saving is obtained due to better steering capacity. This has a double impact as it reduces the maneuvering time and reduces the engine regime changes. This result is extrapolated from the simulation

performed at the USP (Universidade de Sao Paulo) (one full week testing with 3 Captains)

Figure 5 – High performance rudder system

- 5% saving is estimated as a benefit of a much more even load engine regime when combining batteries for the peak shaving.
- 1,7% saving is obtained when taking the electric consumption from the more efficient main gensets in an electric propulsion arrangement.

It has to be mentioned that all these values have been selected on a very conservative approach, taking always the lower value in the range.

4. Maneuverability

A fairly large amount of round-trip time is lost in the maneuvering operations over the numerous river bends with large and fully loaded convoys (290 m long x 64 m wide). Therefore, by improving the steering capabilities of the pusher this maneuvering time can be reduced, avoiding the flanking operation. A simulation performed by Consulmar at the USP Numerical Testing Tank proved that replacing flanking rudders by high performance rudders the maneuvering time could be drastically reduced, permitting to make more round trips/year. Next Figure 6 shows the steering capabilities and Figure 7 present the maneuvering simulation (at many real Parana and Paraguay river bends) developed at the USP and it also compares the conventional (red) flanking maneuver at a river bend with the improved (green) maneuver route using the new steering capabilities (without flanking rudders). It is clear that, apart from the energy savings previously discussed, there is a net gain in time, reducing the overall round-trip time, and therefore increasing the profitability of the whole operation.

The sketch represents the tug + a convoy of 16 jumbo barges.
L = 290 m B = 64 m (950' x 210')
 (barges 61.5 m x 16 m ~ 202' x 52.5')

Turn almost in a spot
 4 rudders at 60°
 B.T. emulating flanking rudders

Starting from speed 0
 Tactical diameter approx. 89 m (292').
 Rate of turn 31°/min

Figure 6 – Impressive Steering Capabilities

Figure 7 – Maneuvering Time Comparison at River Bend
 (last image belongs to Becker Marine)

These results have been obtained without the deck mounted rudder propeller systems proposed as one of the most powerful tools in the Ecopusher® tool kit. Therefore, an equivalent, or even better performance might be obtained for these alternative steering systems.

As the Eureka MCM®@Towboats (Marine Competitiveness Model applied to Towboats) demonstrates, this dramatic improvement in maneuverability has a very high impact in the overall convoy investment. The reason is that, by reducing the maneuvering time at the many dozens of critical bends, the roundtrip duration can be drastically reduced. This allows transporting more cargo per year generating more revenue or, seeing it from another point, it permits to move the same annual amount of cargo with a smaller number of convoys. This means that it is possible to make the same business with a smaller fleet, getting a higher profitability over the invested CAPEX.

5. Minimum Draft

Climate Change is affecting very seriously the inland waterways navigation by reducing the river stages. In the Paraguay- Paraná Waterway (PPW) extreme lower stages are more frequent and last longer. Last decade is a clear example of the new trend. And the fact is that this is not going to get any better; on the contrary, the lack of strength in global environment protection actions is worsening the situation.

The immediate reaction of the river operators is to increase the river dredging efforts, focusing in the critical points of the river. But additional dredging has an economical and physical limit and also affects the environment. Therefore, it makes a lot of sense to reduce the operational minimum draft of the pushers. In order to do that, there are two conditions to be met:

- The minimum draft shall be obtained with realistic vessel load conditions that allows a profitable operation.
- The propellers providing the required thrust shall be completely submerged, performing within acceptable conditions.

Meeting these criteria, Consulmar pushers' designs have reached an ultra-low operational draft of 5'-6" for a gas/electric hybrid 8000 HP towboat, by increasing the beam and the number of shaft lines moving smaller diameter fully immersed propellers. As shown in Figure 8, 9 and 10, the Ecopusher® brings an additional solution: It uses the following two propulsion systems to get the combination of power and draft required for both cases (normal and restricted draft)

- Two pairs of conventional shaft lines are installed with small propellers (5'-6").
- A Deck Mounted Steering Rudder Propeller >6' diameter is installed at Center Line.

Figure 8 – Ultra Low Draft Ecopusher® (Side)

Figure 9 – Ultra Low Draft Ecopusher® (Deck)

Figure 10 – Ultra Low Draft Ecopusher® (Machinery Space)

In normal draft conditions, with a fully loaded convoy both propulsion systems operate providing the full power and steering capacity required for an efficient and safe operation.

But in extreme low draft conditions, with the barges loaded at almost 50%, the Rudder Propeller system is lifted using its telescopic vertical shaft to navigate through the critical areas.

The other four smaller propellers alone provide enough thrust to push the convoy with the reduced cargo.

An additional advantage is that the Deck Mounted Steering Rudder Propeller (SRP) also has a tilting function (dotted lines in Fig 8) that facilitates maintenance and/or repairs without the need of drydocking.

6. Fuel

Over a hundred years ago petroleum-based fuels started to replace carbon for many reasons; among them, manipulation, weight, volume, ashes disposal, and environmental impact. But it was not before the 1950's that Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) became the most popular marine fuel for larger engines and Marine Gas Oil (MGO) for smaller ships. This marine fuel preference is already starting to decrease as stronger international regulations call for a drastic reduction of harmful emissions both for planet and human health.

The Business As Usual (BAU) scenario is not an acceptable one for the globally agreed reduction of Green House Gases (GHG) emissions to reach the necessary reduction of Climate Change effects.

The era of marine fossil fuels (mainly HFO and MGO) is ending but it is still unclear which is going to be the new marine fuel of the future. Most of the experts agree that will be a Green Hydrogen Carrier (Ammonia or Methanol) but they are still very expensive to produce and technology is still under development at an accelerated rhythm.

It is a fact that Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) is the transition fuel, with almost 1000 vessels already built or under construction at this moment (1). Even considering the LNG carriers the percentage of LNG-fueled ships over the 60,000 deep sea vessels is only 4% in number of units and 6% in dwt.

Figure 21 – Growth of LNG-fueled vessels

Figure 12 presents the International Maritime Organization (IMO) projected fuel mix until 2050 ambitions pathway (2). By 2050, it is expected that LNG (light blue) would provide 41% of the energy required for marine transportation, replacing the present preference of MGO + LSFO + HFO (over 85%).

Figure 32 – Projected Marine Energy Fuel Sources

There are three main critics to LNG; the first one is the high infrastructure cost to produce it at small scale, already solved by micro liquefaction plants; second is the CO₂ emissions, reduced only 25%. This can be solved by blending bio-LNG to fossil LNG, getting to net zero. The third critic is the methane slip, but this has already been tackled very well by engines' manufacturers.

There are other green fuels that are also becoming more competitive as shown in Figure 13 (3).

Figure 43 – Projected share of Marine fuels by 2050

Then, which fuel should be chosen for your future vessel? This uncertainty with respect to the "right" marine fuel is solved in the Ecopusher® platform by the adoption of a Future Ready approach that maximizes fuel flexibility.

Operators will choose an initial fuel for their pushers but (by design) these vessels are prepared to change partially or totally to other fuel types in the future with minimum extra CAPEX and very low operational impact.

In the case of the Ecopushers® designed for the Paraguay-Paraná Waterway (PPW), the initial fuel selected is LNG/BioLNG with pure gas engines or dual fuel arrangements, depending on the operators' preferences. Full gas has the advantage of avoiding a critical problem on the PPW: the fuel robbery (estimated in up to 10%!), that does not only affect the OPEX but also has a very negative effect in the crew culture as fuel robbery is the entrance gate to other crimes that involve the crew as smuggling, drug dealing and human trafficking.

As shown in Figure 14, the size of tanks required for the same range varies depending on the fuel type. This is a very critical design aspect for large range operations as those in the WWP that shall connect two extreme terminals almost 1500 nautical miles apart.

The LNG volume for the round trip would be 600 m³ plus some MGO, in case of dual fuel engines. This is a very difficult requirement to meet that gets even worse when combined with the need of an ultra-low draft (5'-6") during the unpredictable drought season.

Figure 54 – Relative Fuel Tank Sizes

Ecopusher® solves this problem with the M-G-Mod® solution designed in partnership with Galileo Technologies, a local company with global reach delivering LNG solutions worldwide.

They have marine experience in LNG production and bunkering having participated in the case of the Fast Ferry Francisco (Figure 15) successfully operating since 2013 in Rio de la Plata.

Figure 65 – Buquebus (www.galileotechnologies.com)

M-G-Mod[®] solution is a fully independent Marine Gas Module, built, tested and classed in factory and mounted on board with the number of LNG isotanks required for the intended service. As shown in Figure 16, the module includes bunkering station, vaporization unit and storage tanks located at the center of the length, close to the center of gravity so that fuel consumption does not affect the trim. Its open-air location minimizes the risks associated to gas leaks, and facilitates erection and dismantling and eases maintenance.

Figure 76 – Ecopusher[®] 600 m³ LNG for 3000 nm range

There is no doubt that LNG/BioLNG will be the most convenient fuel solution for two decades more in the WWP. But by 2045, green H₂ carriers might become interesting alternatives as well, and even better as we get closer to year 2050. In such a case, if the operator prefers to switch partially or totally to another green fuel the Ecopusher[®] will be ready to do it with a low investment and a minimum operational disruption, modifying engines on board, replacing isotanks by others carrying other fuels and the corresponding auxiliary systems.

The “future ready” approach avoids a predictable “future nightmare” and makes easier today’s decision making process, getting the best out the present without resigning the future.

7. Propulsion systems

Among several possible combinations of propulsion systems considered in the Ecopusher[®] platform the main three are the following:

- Conventional mechanical.
- Electrical.
- Deck mounted rudder propeller.

A conventional mechanical system is a series of marine engines direct-mechanically driving shaft-propellers. These engines can be fueled by MGO, IFO, LNG or any other greener fuel at 100% or in a dual fuel arrangement. The engines are installed in the engine room located at the stern. The main advantage is that is the best-known arrangement with lowest initial CAPEX for MGO fueled engines.

An electrical system is a series of marine generator sets that provide energy to an electrical switchboard which distributes it to the different users. The main users are the propulsion electrical engines that will move the shafts and propellers, typically located within an engine room located at the stern. Among the main advantages are the followings:

- The power required by the Master through the power-stick, is available in the propellers almost instantly.
- generator sets do not need to be located at the stern engine room.
- engines’ generators may run at a constant ideal operational regime, drastically reducing consumption and maintenance.
- combined with batteries the energy demand peaks can be shaved.
- on board comfort is improved very much.

On the other hand, the main disadvantages are:

- extra requirements of CAPEX
- energy (losses)
- river crews have little to no experience with these systems.

Deck mounted rudder propeller systems can be electrically or mechanically driven but they always provide some unique advantages that are worth mentioning. Among them, the ease of erection, maintenance and repairs with no need of drydocking. In the case of LNG fueled pushers, having the engines on deck suppresses the risk of gas losses, a major issue to take into account in these cases.

outfitting stage, with the vessel already launched.

- The Accommodation can be fabricated as an independent module and be erected on top the hull after hull launching. In this case, modularity reaches an even higher level as the whole accommodation is designed to be formed by nine 40' ISO containers that could be built at a specialized shop arriving to the final destination after launching.

This modularity concept reduces the typically high dependence on only one main shipyard, improving the contract negotiation power and permitting to split the whole construction project in a series of smaller subcontracts to different specialized selected contractors with ideal combination of best quality, lower prices and reduced delivery times.

The obvious benefits of this approach are obtained only if the Design & Project Management Teams work as one: this is the Eureka approach, adding also the LNG bunkering and Bare Boat Chartering as shown in the Figure 18.

Figure 18 – The Eureka Approach

This modularity concept has the advantage of maximum flexibility, it allows making changes that would be very complicated with the conventional construction approaches.

Some of the flexibility cases are the following ones:

- To modify fuel capacity to meet the range required that may vary in future routes, avoiding carrying unnecessary tanks on board if range is reduced.
- To combine different fuels or even batteries and/or fuel cells in ISO containers using available slots in the MGM.
- To replace the complete steering rudder propulsion systems in very short time without need of drydocking.

10. Performance Follow Up

The Eureka approach includes the follow-up of the Ecopusher® operation with the following three main services:

- Crew training during last construction phase and early operation is organized and coordinated by Eureka team, using the most advanced training tools (Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, etc.) for different stages of the operation.
- Experienced superintendents trained in the new technologies will be present on board in the initial operational phases until the crew is comfortable enough.
- During the Ecopusher® design, construction and operation, Digital Twins Technology will be used to develop and enrich Eureka's own integrated system named DIGITWINS®. The Ship Operator, Eureka Team, and the OEM Service Centers will receive on line, the real time performance information of Ecopusher® and its main equipment. This allows to monitor all key systems, minimizing operational breakdowns, reducing maintenance costs and improving planning.

Figure 19 – Digitwins® and Performance Follow-up

11. References

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